
B PLAN ON AGRICULTURAL AND FOOD PROCESSING – CASE WITH RESPECT TO FARM TO HOME B - PLAN

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Abstract:

The basic understanding of this paper is to study the agricultural and food processing in dharwad district. An agricultural food processing sector is rapidly developing in India. It is a major sector which is giving profits for GDP and 70% of the people are depending on agriculture. Agriculture in food process is giving Business plan opportunities for the youth to come up with their innovative and creative ideas with updated technologies which it is also helping the farmers to gain profits to survive. Food processing is developing in its own way with nutrition food supply with quality and quantity based goods with hygiene, good packaging, cold storage facility, by preserving and delivering within a period of time. The idea of food processing mainly helping hands for the rural area people were they believe in agriculture. Agriculture is a backbone to live their life with livelihood. Food processing playing an important role in meeting the customer needs with a healthy supply of products.

Keywords: Agricultural; Food Processing; Packaging and Cold Storage.

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1. Introduction

Food Processing Industry (FPI) in India is a sunrise sector that has gained reputation in the recent years. Easy availability of raw materials, changing lifestyle and favourable fiscal policies has given a considerable push to the industry's growth. FPI serves as a vital association between the agriculture and manufacturing sector of the company. Underpinning this link is critical to reduce wastage of agricultural raw materials, improve the value of agricultural produce by increasing shelf-life as well as by stimulating the nutritive value of the food products and ensure remunerative prices to farmers as well as reasonable price to consumers.

Agricultural food process gives an opportunity to come up with business plan in the name of **Farm to Home**. **Farm to Home** is a start-up business which is basically a online vegetable and fruits selling business. **Farm to Home** enables farmers sell their produce products directly to retail shops, restaurants and individual customers. **Farm to Home** have a services of Business to Business and Business to Customer.

Farm to Home Services Private Limited - Wholesaler of featured products, vegetables & other products in Karnataka. The company can have a network of more than 1,000 surrounding farmers. The portal also provides data feeds to these farmers about which crop to be grown where and when to grow and what fertilizer should be used – to get the optimal price from the market. It can work with farm produce organizations.

Farm to Home says, “Eating fruits and vegetables with harmful pesticides can cause deadly diseases like cancer”. Therefore, start- up delivers farm-fresh, organic, chemical-free and refrigerator-packed fruits and vegetables at customers’ doorstep. Customers can place orders through the venture’s customer care number or through its website.

2. Objective of Agricultural and Food Proceeding

The major objective of this B-plan is to help the farmers as we know that farmers are committing suicide because of the rise in the price level and the consumers end are not reaching them and also agents are making money by demanding high price for hybrid goods . We are trying to give minimum based price for farmers so they can afford and also give buyback assurance once the customer base grows. Mainly looking towards at North Karnataka farmers were they are facing problems with kalasabanduri in cities like: Hubli, Nargund, Navalgund and surrounding areas. And also making farmers to understand about the customers demand for supply of products and helping them to know what all are the required technologies to use in the agricultural sector.

- **Our Mission:** To provide Organic and chemical free Vegetables and Fruits to the Society and help to healthy society.
- **Our vision:** A quality product.

3. Procedures About the Company

3.1. Product

Product procurement process is responsible of Procurement team (W1). The team will start to procure from a farmer who is particularly assigned by Farm to Home. Team collects the vegetables and fruits. If all the requirements are available then product procurement is processed and product will arrive to Farm to Home. If vegetables and fruits are not available as per the indent requirements, collect required goods in APMC.

3.2. Promotion

Promotion process is responsibility of Field Executives (F1). The promotion is done for both Business to Business (B2B) and Business to Customer (B2C). Farm to Home target B2B to fulfill their day-to-day requirements & also target B2C to get working women's. The promotion process is done to B2B keeping stalls in public, exhibition and promotion process is done to B2C approaching door to door directly with pamphlet. B2B customers are Hotels, General Stores & Temples. B2C customers are Apartments, Banks & Garments. After approaching give the detail explanation of products, prices of products like minimum orders, discount & offers and details of delivery. And then collect the contact number of customers for database.

3.3. Pricing

Pricing process is responsibility of CEO & COO. Purchase prices are taken into consideration and also addition of grading and transportation charges and minimum profits percentage.

3.4. Indent

Indent process is responsibility of Operation Manager (M1). Inventory is received from farmers at Farm to Home. Once the inventory is received physical inspection of received goods against indent is done, order reconciliation is done. Then the classification of vegetables and fruits will be conducted according to grades. Vegetables and Fruits are graded as Grade A & Grade B. Then, if expected quantity is available, the indent order is processed. If there is shortage of quantity of goods, then required goods are purchased from sources at APMC

3.5. Order Receiving

Receiving the orders is responsibility of Tele caller /CRM. Orders are received through Call, SMS, Whatsapp & App. Once the orders are received, are entered into Farm to Home software with respect to B2B & B2C. Indent and order sheet are obtained.

3.6. Deliver

Delivery process is responsibility of Operation Manager. Operation Manager assigns each order to the supervisors according to B2B & B2C. The packaging is done according to individual order. The B2B & B2C orders are classified and billing is done accordingly. Loading of vehicle and mapping is done and dispatched. If orders are delivered on scheduled time then order is processed. If any problem occurs then the adjustment for vehicle and orders are delivered. Once all the goods are as per customer’s expectation, then deliver the goods and collect money through Cash in hand, Paytm or Point of sale (Swipe). If customer wants to replace or return, then deduct the price of replaced or returned goods. Then return of (empty) vehicle to the FARM To HOME. Customer comments (voice) are recorded to operation manager. The vehicles collect the empty trays and return to Farm to Home.

3.7. Inventory Management

Inventory Management process is also responsibility of Operation Manager. After delivering the orders, the next step is to weigh all the remaining goods. If all the goods are usable then it is stored in refrigerator. If goods are unusable, then it is treated as dump.

Benefits by Farm to Home Food Processing

- Direct marketing is available for the farmers to their produced products.
- Reduces the middlemen or agents who gain the profits/commissions.
- Reduces the transportation charge of farmers.
- Satisfies the customers demand with quality, quantity to their door step.

Customers can save their time by ordering with App, Websites given by Farm to Home.

4. Conclusion

Farm to Home food processing is implemented a new technologies for preserving, processing, packing, storing and delivering foods. In upcoming days India will play major role to export food products and food grains to other countries. The industry want to develop the ways to process preserve, package, or store food according to industry and government regulations by meeting the standards of quality, safety and nutrition food supply. This giving chance to the products of farmers which give them a profit for their investment did on farm. B plan consist of online vegetable and fruits selling business which effectively helps the farmers and also included the process of procurement promotion and marketing. This B Plan gives opportunities for farmer to grow and get value for their products in the market and this gives a chance for a graduation to start a business. And in this generation everyone need to save their time mainly for working women.

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